

IN-VITRO ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY OF SIDDHA FORMULATION MUTHU PARPAM WITH BRAHMI NEI

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Abstract

The Siddha system of medicine, a holistic traditional medical system, emphasizes both preventive and curative healthcare through plant-based, mineral and animal-derived formulations. Among its therapeutic branches, *Kaya Karpam* (rejuvenation therapy) is recognized for promoting longevity and overall vitality, primarily due to its antioxidant properties. Antioxidants play a crucial role in inhibiting oxidative processes that generate free radicals, thereby preventing cellular damage and the onset of various chronic disorders, including cardiovascular diseases, cancer, neurodegenerative conditions, and inflammatory disorders.

The present study evaluates the antioxidant potential of a classical Siddha formulation Muthu Parpam (MP) with Brahmi Nei (BN). MP, which combines a herbo-mineral preparation derived from the marine mollusc *Pinctada margaritifera* (pearl) with BN, a polyherbal ghee-based preparation (MP-BN)⁽¹⁾. Antioxidant activity was assessed using *in vitro* free radical scavenging assays, including 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), Nitric Oxide, 2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid) (ABTS) and Hydrogen Peroxide Scavenging Assay. MP-BN demonstrated inhibition percentages of 61.46% (DPPH), 41.12% (Nitric Oxide), 36.07% (ABTS), and 39.42% (Hydrogen Peroxide) at 100 µg/ml, compared to standard antioxidants ascorbic acid (88.37%), gallic acid (92.71%, 95.82%), and Butylated Hydroxyanisole (BHA) (86.45%), respectively. Traditionally, MP-BN has been indicated for a

wide range of acute and chronic conditions to enhance endogenous antioxidant levels while reducing lipid peroxidation.

The findings of this study reveal that MP-BN has high natural antioxidant activity, which validates its traditional use as a rejuvenating drug in Siddha medicine. Its capacity to reduce oxidative stress highlights its potential involvement in avoiding free radical-mediated diseases and promoting overall health.

Keywords : Muthu Parpam, Brahmi Nei, antioxidant activity, Siddha

Introduction

In the human body, reactive oxygen species (ROS) are produced naturally during metabolism and also generated by external factors such as pollution and chemicals. When present in excess, they can damage vital biomolecules like DNA, proteins, and lipids, leading to conditions such as heart disease, cancer, neurodegenerative disorders, arthritis, and early aging. Normally, our body defends itself with antioxidant enzymes like superoxide dismutase and catalase, as well as compounds such as vitamin C, vitamin E, flavonoids, and polyphenols. However, when this defense is overwhelmed, oxidative stress occurs, increasing the risk of chronic illness, particularly as age advances. Although synthetic antioxidants like BHA and BHT are effective, concerns about their safety have shifted attention towards natural sources, which are rich in carotenoids, polyphenols, and flavonoids. Siddha medicine have long relied on such therapeutic formulations for preventing oxidative damage and promoting health.

Muthu Parpam (MP), a unique herbo-mineral preparation, described in classical Siddha literature *Siddha Vaithiya Thirattu* and has been used to treat pediatric neurobehavioral disorders. Scientific investigations have revealed that *Muthu Parpam* contains calcium nanoparticles along with other trace elements, and is free from harmful heavy metals^(2,4). At the classical therapeutic dose of 260 mg, it has been considered safe for oral administration⁽³⁾. Traditionally, it has been used for a wide range of conditions, including asthma, eye disorders, and neuromuscular diseases.

Brahmi Nei (BN) is a well-known polyherbal preparation in the Siddha system which is traditionally indicated for improving memory, alleviating nervous debility, reducing anxiety, and controlling convulsions. In Siddha philosophy, oxidative stress is recognized as a major cause of degenerative illnesses, premature aging, and chronic diseases such as cardiovascular

disorders, diabetes, and neurodegenerative conditions. These effects are believed to arise from the antioxidant and free radical scavenging activity of its herbal constituents.

Given that both *Muthu Parpam* and *Brahmi Nei* are valued for their rejuvenative and restorative actions, combining them (MP-BN) offers a distinctive Siddha therapeutic strategy aimed at combating oxidative stress. This study was therefore designed to evaluate the antioxidant potential of MP-BN through in vitro free radical scavenging assays, with the aim of substantiating traditional claims and exploring possible applications in oxidative stress-related diseases.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study drug was purchased from GMP certified Siddha pharmaceutical company.

Table 1. Ingredients of Muthu parpam

S.No	Drug	Botanical Name/Scientific name
1	Muthu	<i>Pinctada margaritifera</i>
2	Notchi	<i>Vitex negundo</i>
3	Nilapanai kizhanghu	<i>Curculigo orchioides</i>

Table 2. Ingredients of Brahmi Nei

S.No	Drug Name	Botanical Name/Scientific name
1	Brahmi	<i>Bacopa monnieri</i>
2	Vasambu	<i>Acorus calamus</i>
3	Arathai	<i>Alpinia officinarum</i>
4	Sivathai ver	<i>Operculina turpethum</i>
5	Chukku	<i>Zinger officinale</i>
6	Thippili	<i>Piper longum</i>
7	Nelli vatal	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>
8	Vila vithai	<i>Limonia acidissima</i>
9	Inthuppu	<i>Sodium chloridum impura</i>
10	Kasthuri manjal	<i>Curcuma longa</i>
11	Seena karkandu	-
12	Pasum paal	-
13	Pasu nei	-

The purchased drug was subjected to the following antioxidant assays.

DPPH (2, 2-Diphenyl 1-2 picrylhydrazyl) Assay^(5, 6)

The antioxidant activity of test drug sample MP-BN was determined using the 2,2-diphenyl 1-2 picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) free radical scavenging assay. Sample MP-BN at the concentration of 10 -100 µg/ml along with standard ascorbic acid were utilized for detection of DPPH scavenging assay. Final reaction mixture containing 1 ml of 0.3 mM DPPH methanol solution was added to 2.5 ml of sample solution of different concentrations and allowed to react at room temperature. Absorbance in the presence of test sample MP-BN at different concentration of (10 µg, 20 µg, 40 µg, 60 µg, 80 µg and 100µg/ml) was noted after 15 min incubation period at 37°C. Absorbance was read out at 517 nm using double-beam U.V Spectrophotometer by using methanol as blank.

$$\text{Radical scavenging (\%)} = \left[\frac{(A)_{\text{control}} - (A)_{\text{sample}}}{(A)_{\text{control}}} \right] \times 100.$$

The effective concentration of test sample MP-BN required to scavenge DPPH radical by 50% (IC₅₀ value) was obtained by linear regression analysis of dose-response curve plotting between %inhibition and concentrations.

Nitric Oxide Radical Scavenging Assay^(7, 8)

The concentrations of test sample MP-BN are made into serial dilution from 10–100 µg/mL and the standard gallic acid. Griess reagent was prepared by mixing equal amounts of 1% sulphanilamide in 2.5% phosphoric acid and 0.1% naphthylethylene diamine dihydrochloride in 2.5% phosphoric acid immediately before use. A volume of 0.5 mL of 10 mM sodium nitroprusside in phosphate buffered saline was mixed with 1 mL of the different concentrations of the test drug (10–100 µg/mL) and incubated at 25°C for 180 mins. The test drug MP-BN was mixed with an equal volume of freshly prepared Griess reagent. Control samples without the test drug but with an equal volume of buffer were prepared in a similar manner as was done for the test samples. The absorbance was measured at 546 nm using a Spectra Max Plus UV-Vis microplate reader (Molecular Devices, GA, USA). Gallic acid was used as the positive control. The percentage inhibition of the test drug MP-BN and standard

was calculated and recorded. The percentage nitrite radical scavenging activity of the test drug MP-BN and gallic acid were calculated using the following formula:

percentage nitrite radical scavenging activity:

$$\text{nitric oxide scavenged (\%)} = \frac{A_{\text{control}} - A_{\text{test}}}{A_{\text{control}}} \times 100,$$

where A_{control} = absorbance of control sample and A_{test} = absorbance in the presence of the samples extracts or standards.

ABTS Assay ⁽⁹⁾

This assay carried out for the purpose of evaluating the anti-oxidant potential of test drug MP-BN against 2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonic acid) or ABTS radicals. The ABTS radical cation method was modified to evaluate the free radical-scavenging effect of one hundred pure chemical compounds. The ABTS reagent was prepared by mixing 5 mL of 7 mM ABTS with 88 μL of 140 mM potassium persulfate. The mixture was then kept in the dark at room temperature for 16 h to allow free radical generation and was then diluted with water (1 : 44, v/v). To determine the scavenging activity, 100 μL ABTS reagent was mixed with 100 μL of test sample at the concentration of 10-100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ in DD water and was incubated at room temperature for 6 min. After incubation, the absorbance was measured 734 nm. 100% methanol was used as a control. Gallic acid with same concentrations of test drug MP-BN was measured following the same procedures described above and was used as positive controls. The antioxidant activity of the test sample MP-BN was calculated using the following equation: The ABTS scavenging effect was measured using the following formula:

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Radical scavenging (\%)} \\ &= \left[\frac{(A)_{\text{control}} - (A)_{\text{sample}}}{(A)_{\text{control}}} \right] \times 100. \end{aligned}$$

Hydrogen Peroxide Radical Scavenging Assay ^(10, 11)

A hydrogen peroxide solution (2 mM) was prepared in 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). Aliquots (0.1 mL) of the test sample MP-BN (different concentration ranging from 10-100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) were transferred into the test tubes and their volumes were made up to 0.4 mL with 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). After adding 0.6 mL hydrogen peroxide solution, tubes were

vortexed and the absorbance of the hydrogen peroxide at 230 nm was determined after 10 min, against a blank. BHA was used as the positive control. The percentage inhibition of the test drug MP-BN and standard was calculated and recorded. The percentage radical scavenging activity of the test drug MP-BN and BHA were calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Radical scavenging (\%)} = \left[\frac{(A)_{\text{control}} - (A)_{\text{sample}}}{(A)_{\text{control}}} \right] \times 100$$

Results

Table 3. Percentage inhibition of test drug MP-BN on DPPH radical scavenging assay

Concentration (µg/ml)	% Inhibition of MP-BN	% Inhibition of Ascorbic Acid
10 µg/ml	14.97 ± 10.42	20.9 ± 11.23
20 µg/ml	24.2 ± 6.764	27.64 ± 10.91
40 µg/ml	34.08 ± 10.58	49.31 ± 6.47
60 µg/ml	41.45 ± 15.06	61.7 ± 7.068
80 µg/ml	55.19 ± 6.292	73.23 ± 10.95
100 µg/ml	61.46 ± 4.248	88.37 ± 5.845

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

Table 4. IC50 Values for DPPH radical scavenging Assay by MP-BN and standard.

Test Drug / Standard	IC50 Value DPPH Assay ± SD (µg /ml)
MP-BN	73.23 ± 16.24
ASCORBIC ACID	46.67 ± 12.18

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

Table 5. Percentage inhibition of test drug MP-BN on Nitric Oxide radical scavenging assay

Concentration (µg/ml)	% Inhibition of MP-BN	% Inhibition of Gallic Acid
10 µg/ml	6.009 ± 1.705	24.33 ± 4.717
20 µg/ml	12.16 ± 2.548	38.7 ± 7.502
40 µg/ml	17.19 ± 2.242	51.45 ± 2.985
60 µg/ml	24.18 ± 2.062	57.43 ± 2.931
80 µg/ml	33.05 ± 5.187	82.06 ± 2.867
100 µg/ml	41.12 ± 8.983	92.71 ± 1.484

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

Table 6. IC50 Values for Nitric Oxide radical scavenging assay by MP-BN and standard.

Test Drug / Standard	IC50 Value NO Assay ± SD (µg /ml)
MP-BN	128.2 ± 22.17
GALLIC ACID	40.77 ± 5.824

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

Table 7. Percentage inhibition of test drug MP-BN on ABTS radical scavenging assay

Concentration (µg/ml)	% Inhibition of MP-BN	% Inhibition of Gallic Acid
10 µg/ml	8.552 ± 2.223	29.52 ± 2.324
20 µg/ml	13.09 ± 1.279	52.59 ± 1.239
40 µg/ml	18.57 ± 3.638	61.41 ± 0.3509
60 µg/ml	24.38 ± 5.184	77.78 ± 0.3334
80 µg/ml	28.44 ± 4.596	85.52 ± 0.7898
100 µg/ml	36.07 ± 5.508	95.82 ± 0.9762

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

Table 8. IC50 Values for ABTS radical scavenging assay by MP-BN and standard.

Test Drug / Standard	IC50 Value ABTS Assay ± SD (µg /ml)
MP-BN	155.5 ± 32.41
GALLIC ACID	26.34 ± 1.916

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

Table 9. Percentage inhibition of test drug MP-BN on Hydrogen peroxide radical scavenging assay

Concentration (µg/ml)	% Inhibition of MP-BN	% Inhibition of BHA
10 µg/ml	5.729 ± 3.277	26.24 ± 3.289
20 µg/ml	12.19 ± 2.158	39.85 ± 4.509
40 µg/ml	17.35 ± 3.204	52.25 ± 2.547
60 µg/ml	26.52 ± 2.029	57.88 ± 6.078
80 µg/ml	30.97 ± 3.644	72.25 ± 2.213
100 µg/ml	39.42 ± 5.297	86.45 ± 7.597

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

Table 10. IC50 Values for Hydrogen peroxide radical scavenging assay by MP-BN and standard.

Test Drug / Standard	IC50 Value Hydrogen peroxide radical scavenging Assay ± SD (µg /ml)
MP-BN	130.9 ± 14.26
BHA	42.28 ± 5.434

Data are given as Mean ± SD (n=3)

Discussion

In this study, the combined Siddha formulation *Muthu parpam with Brahmi Nei* (MP-BN) was evaluated for its in vitro antioxidant potential, with an emphasis on its possible application in oxidative stress-related disorders.

In the present investigation, MP-BN exhibited measurable free radical scavenging activity across all four tested assays, though the potency varied when compared to standard antioxidants. In the DPPH assay, MP-BN showed moderate activity, with percentage inhibition rising from $14.97 \pm 10.42\%$ at $10 \mu\text{g/ml}$ to $61.46 \pm 4.248\%$ at $100 \mu\text{g/ml}$. The IC_{50} value of $73.23 \pm 16.24 \mu\text{g/ml}$ was higher than that of ascorbic acid ($46.67 \pm 12.18 \mu\text{g/ml}$), indicating lower potency but clear dose-dependent activity. Since the DPPH assay measures the ability of compounds to donate hydrogen atoms and stabilize free radicals, these findings suggest that MP-BN has a reasonable capacity to neutralize stable free radicals, supporting its traditional use in oxidative stress-mediated disorders.

The nitric oxide radical scavenging assay revealed a more modest activity profile, with inhibition increasing from $6.009 \pm 1.705\%$ to $41.12 \pm 8.983\%$ across the tested concentrations. The IC_{50} value ($128.2 \pm 22.17 \mu\text{g/ml}$) was substantially higher than that of gallic acid ($40.77 \pm 5.824 \mu\text{g/ml}$), indicating that MP-BN is a relatively weak scavenger of nitric oxide radicals. Since nitric oxide overproduction has been implicated in inflammatory and neurodegenerative conditions, the observed low NO scavenging efficiency may limit MP-BN direct role in such pathologies.

In the ABTS assay, which measures both hydrophilic and lipophilic antioxidant capacity, MP-BN demonstrated weak activity ($8.552 \pm 2.223\%$ to $36.07 \pm 5.508\%$), with an IC_{50} value of $155.5 \pm 32.41 \mu\text{g/ml}$ compared to $26.34 \pm 1.916 \mu\text{g/ml}$ for gallic acid. This suggests that while MP-BN possesses ABTS radical scavenging properties, its efficiency is far below that of the standard, implying limited contribution in contexts dominated by ABTS-type radicals.

The hydrogen peroxide scavenging assay showed a similar pattern, with MP-BN activity increasing from $5.729 \pm 3.277\%$ at $10 \mu\text{g/ml}$ to $39.42 \pm 5.297\%$ at $100 \mu\text{g/ml}$. However, the IC_{50} value of $130.9 \pm 14.26 \mu\text{g/ml}$ was markedly higher than that of BHA ($42.28 \pm 5.434 \mu\text{g/ml}$), reflecting comparatively low peroxide neutralization potential. As hydrogen peroxide readily diffuses across membranes and can generate highly reactive hydroxyl radicals via the Fenton reaction, the moderate scavenging ability of MP-BN may offer some degree of cellular protection, but not at the level of potent synthetic antioxidants.

Muthu parpam combined with Brami nei (MP-BN) demonstrated in-vitro antioxidant activity across a panel of free-radical assays (DPPH, ABTS, nitric oxide and hydrogen peroxide scavenging). Although the formulation scavenged radicals in a concentration-dependent manner, its IC₅₀ values (DPPH 73.23 ± 16.24 µg/mL; NO 128.2 ± 22.17 µg/mL; ABTS 155.5 ± 32.41 µg/mL; H₂O₂ 130.9 ± 14.26 µg/mL) were consistently higher than those of the respective reference antioxidants (standard IC₅₀s: DPPH 46.67 ± 12.18; NO 40.77 ± 5.82; ABTS 26.34 ± 1.92; BHA 42.28 ± 5.43 µg/mL), indicating lower in-vitro potency. The magnitude of difference varied by assay (test was ~1.6× weaker in DPPH, ~3.1× weaker in NO and H₂O₂, and ~5.9× weaker in ABTS), which likely reflects differential reactivity of the formulation's phytochemicals toward discrete radical species. Given that oxidative stress is implicated in the pathophysiology of many neurological disorders, the observed antioxidant capacity provides a plausible mechanistic basis for the traditional use of this formulation in neurological conditions. However, because these results derive from cell-free chemical assays, they do not account for bioavailability, metabolism, blood–brain barrier permeability, cellular uptake, or possible synergistic interactions in biological systems. Therefore, while the in-vitro data are encouraging, in-cellulo and in-vivo neuroprotective studies, along with phytochemical characterization and standardization, are required to evaluate therapeutic relevance.

Conclusion

Muthu parpam combined with Brami nei (MP-BN) possesses demonstrable radical-scavenging activity in multiple in-vitro antioxidant assays, supporting its traditional use as a supportive agent in neurological disorders where oxidative stress contributes to pathogenesis. However, the formulation is less potent than standard antioxidants in these assays. Further work including phytochemical profiling, dose-response studies with larger replicate numbers, cell-based oxidative stress and neuroprotection assays, in-vivo efficacy/safety testing, and ADME/BBB permeability studies is required to establish clinical relevance and therapeutic potential.

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